

Latin American Contribution to JUNO

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Abstract

The Jiangmen Underground Neutrino Observatory (JUNO) is 20 kton multipurpose underground Liquid Scintillator detector located at about 53 km away from two high power nuclear complexes in southern China. Designed to have unprecedented energy resolution, it will have a vast physics reach including the Neutrino Mass Hierarchy determination, precision measurement of oscillation parameters, detection of galactic Supernova (SN) burst neutrinos, detection of Diffuse supernova neutrino background (DSNB) among others. Latin American institutions are mostly involved in the SPMT subsystem aimed at implementing Double-Calorimetry and allowing a better control of systematic uncertainties. Contributions both in hardware (mostly in the Under Water Boxes and High-Voltage Splitters) and software (simulation and analysis) are ongoing.

Tematic Areas Neutrino Physics; Instrumentation and Computing;

1 Scientific Context

Neutrinos ([10] and references therein) produced in nuclear reactors provide a fundamental tool to explore neutrino physics. Their study allowed the first detection of Neutrinos as a free particle by Reines and Cowan in the '50, almost 30 years after Pauli's prediction. More recently the KamLAND experiment in the 2000s showed that Solar Neutrino Problem was indeed caused by oscillation and that oscillation also occurs in reactor neutrinos. The last generation of large reactor neutrinos experiments (notably Daya Bay, Double Chooz and RENO) finally measured the last mixing angle θ_{13} , while experiments under construction

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have the opportunity to determine the Neutrino Mass Hierarchy and investigate the existence of Sterile Neutrinos.

Latin American institutions have been participating to this fascinating research since the 2000s with contributions to both the Daya Bay [5] and Double Chooz [3] experiments. Moreover a significant investment in local infrastructure paved the way toward measurements of reactor neutrinos in Latin America with the ongoing Neutrinos Angra [8] and CONNIE [4] projects. These local projects, although small, seems to be crucial if a future leading role within the international community has to be achieved. Probably more important for the Latin America community is however the participation to the JUNO collaboration [6], which is today the most important reactor neutrino experiment under construction.

According to reference [7] (pg.104) the international neutrino community is oriented as follow: "The first priority is today on the completion of the program of measurements of the oscillation parameters, most notably the CP-violating phase of the mixing matrix and the neutrino mass ordering. Two strong and complementary experimental programmes are in preparation towards this goal in the US and Japan with the DUNE and Hyper-Kamiokande experiments." It must be considered however that for example [9] "DUNE will reach 5σ sensitivity to the neutrino mass ordering for any value of δ_{CP} and it will be able to discover CP violation in the leptonic sector at 3σ for 50% of δ_{CP} values" after "10 years of operations". Moreover "operation will start in 2026".

Concerning the determination of the neutrino mass ordering there are other two complementary experimental techniques: one based on medium baseline reactor neutrinos like in the JUNO observatory [6], and one based on a high-statistical measurement of atmospheric neutrinos like in PINGU [1]. It has been pointed out recently [2] that in a joint JUNO-PINGU "the inverted ordering could be excluded within 1.5 years (3 years for the normal ordering)". The much shorter schedule of these two complementary approaches makes them extremely attractive from an experimental point of view.

We first of all discuss the objectives of the JUNO observatory. The methodology is therefore described, with special emphasis to the Small Photo-Multipliers subsystem (SPMTs). Then we present the ongoing and planned Latin American contributions to this subsystem, the list of the interested scientists in the community and the current status and expected challenges. Finally we present the timeline, construction and operational costs and computing requirements.

2 Objectives

A list of important physical objectives of the JUNO observatory includes:

- **Neutrino Mass Hierarchy determination:** discussed below.
- **Precision measurement of oscillation parameters:** discussed below.
- **Detection of Supernova Neutrino Burst:** it is expected to have about one SN burst in our galaxy every 30 years. JUNO, thanks to a combination

of its unique size and energy resolution, will be capable to provide precious insight to such an event.

- **Diffuse Supernova Neutrino Background (DSNB):** Large Liquid Scintillator detectors offers a promising tools to detect this long-sought cosmogenic background.
- **Solar Neutrino:** thanks to its energy resolution, threshold and detector size JUNO is an attractive experiment to shed light in issues such as the solar metallicity problem and the transition between vacuum dominated and MSW-dominated oscillation mechanism. To achieve this goal however a dedicated effort for a low background phase is necessary.
- **Geo-neutrino:** JUNO allow the detection of about 300-500 geo-neutrinos per year.
- **Proton decay:** JUNO has the potential to provide important information on decay channels such as $P \rightarrow K + \nu$.

Concerning the first two items, which are related to Neutrino Oscillations, it is useful to keep in mind an approximate formula for reactor electron anti-neutrino survival probability in a medium baseline (~ 50 km):

$$P(\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e) = 1 - \sin^2 2\theta_{12} c_{13}^4 \sin^2 \frac{\Delta m_{21}^2 L}{4E} - \sin^2 2\theta_{13} \left[c_{12}^2 \sin^2 \frac{\Delta m_{31}^2 L}{4E} + s_{12}^2 \sin^2 \frac{\Delta m_{32}^2 L}{4E} \right], \quad (1)$$

where $c_{ij} \equiv \cos \theta_{ij}$, $s_{ij} \equiv \sin \theta_{ij}$, $\Delta m_{ij}^2 \equiv m_i^2 - m_j^2$ (for $ij = 12, 13, 23$) and E and L are neutrino energy and path length (production to detection) respectively.

When the survival probability is multiplied by the reactor anti-neutrino energy spectra we get energy spectra such as those illustrated in 1. It is clear that the determination of the mass hierarchy from the study of shape differences requires both large statistical samples and excellent energy resolution. It is important to notice that for precise determination of the oscillation "solar parameters", θ_{12} and δm_{12} , the energy resolution requirement can be somewhat relaxed. We will discuss the impact of these requirements to the detector design in the next section.

3 Methodology

It has been discussed in the previous section that JUNO has the potential to address a wide spectrum of physical questions. The measurement of the neutrino mass hierarchy imposes however to strongest requirements to the detector design:

- large statistics of reactor neutrino events (more than $\sim 10^5$)

Figure 1: The relative shape of the reactor anti-neutrino flux for different values of the oscillation parameters.

- well defined reactor-detector length of about 53 km (the reactor-detector distance should be very similar to most reactors)
- unprecedented energy resolution (3% at 1MeV)
- low energy scale uncertainty (below 1%)

In order to satisfy the first two requirements the experimental site in Kaiping, Jiangmen, in Southern China has been chosen. The detector will be located under the Dashi hill with about 700 m of rock overburden. The nuclear power plants of Yangjiang (4 cores) and Taishan (6 cores) will provide a total of 35.8MW of thermal power with all reactors in operation modes. The detector (fig. 2) will have about 20 kton of active mass of Linear Alkyl Benzen (LAB) scintillator, close to the limit of what is cost effective from a civil construction point of view.

Concerning the last two detector requirements, the task is to keep the neutrino energy measurement both very accurate and precise. This will be accomplished by the use of two systems of photo-multipliers:

- Large Photo-Multipliers (LPMTs), a set of 18000 3" photo-multipliers, providing a coverage of about 73% and working in "charge integration mode", necessary to control the stochastic uncertainty of the energy resolution
- Small Photo-Multipliers (SPMTs), a set of 25000 3" photo-multipliers, designed to have a better single photo-electron resolution in order to work

in "photon-counting mode", will provide better control of the systematic uncertainties of the energy measurements.

Also the quality of the scintillator must be unprecedented in terms of light-yield and absorption length.

Other important parts of the JUNO detector are: the acrylic sphere (containing the scintillator) and its support structure, the calibration system and veto detectors, composed by the water Cherenkov pool (acting as a shield as well) and the top tracker.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the JUNO detector.

The SPMTs objectives are mostly: improve the neutrino energy reconstruction and the muon reconstruction resolution, provide an almost independent precision measurement of the θ_{12} and Δm_{21}^2 solar oscillation parameters and finally improve the sensitivity of the neutrino mass hierarchy measurement. Their main components (Fig. 3) are the photo-multipliers (XP72B22 by Hainan Zhanchuang Photonics Co., HZC), the under-water boxes (UWB, see next section), the H.V. splitters (HVS, see next section), ABC front-end electronics (for Data Acquisition), power supply and Global Control Units (for data transfer and related tasks).

4 Planned Latin American Contributions

The Latin American activities within the JUNO collaboration are focused on the SPMT system, with both hardware and software contributions. In particular the Chile Team work is devoted to the high-voltage splitter (HVS) and the

underwater box (UWB), while the Brazilian work is devoted the ABC board simulation and the analysis of sensitivity to the solar oscillation parameters.

4.1 HVS

The HVS is an electronics board that serves multiple purposes: + To provide the high voltage (HV) supply to the SPMTs. The HV supply is generated by a redundant system of HV units (HVUs), which are commercial DC-DC converters developed by Marathon in Russia. + To decouple the PMT signals from the HV lines. The decoupled PMT signals also include overvoltage protections. These lines are fed into the ABC readout boards, which are being developed in Bordeaux and include CATIROC front-end and readout chips produced by Omega. + To serve as a motherboard for the HVUs, handling their configuration and redundant operation. The HVUs are configured from the GCU board, which will be connected to the HVS.

Each HVS board has 64 independent HV high-pass filters, carefully designed and tuned to match the SPMT impedance in order to keep the signal integrity. The 64 SPMTs are connected to the HVS board using an array of 64 MCX high-voltage RF connectors. The HVS board also holds 8 HVUs. Each redundant pair of HVUs serves 16 SPMTs.

Since the ABC board is designed for 128 SPMT channels, two HVS boards are required per ABC board. The ABC board, the GCU board and both HVS boards will be securely connected and housed inside an UWB. The connection between the UWB and the SPMTs is done using 8 electrical harnesses, each serving 16 PMTs, and designed for underwater hermeticity. A high-level block diagram of the ABC-GCU-HVSx2 electronics system is shown in Fig.3 .

Figure 3: High-level block diagram of SPMT readout system. Credit: Pablo Walker.

4.2 UWB

The Underwater box consists of a stainless steel receptacle that must keep the circuits of sPMT in a safe environment, since the UWB is going to be submerged on ultra pure water for over 20 years. This box has to perform not only to keep the circuits safe against water over 20 years, but also it has to resist corrosion over the same period, resist pressure between 0 to 7 bars, have low magnetism and heat dissipation characteristics.

A total of 220 UWBs equipped with electronics will be produced and installed in the periphery of the JUNO central detector.

4.3 Simulation and Analysis

On the simulation side the Brazilian groups are involved in developing the code for the SPMT electronic simulation, specifically describing all physical effects that occurs between the generation of photo-electrons in SPMT photo cathodes up to the storage on tape of digitized signals. The simulation should therefore correctly describe effects such as:

- PMT related effects such as transit time, dynode amplification and after-pulses
- Cable and connectors effects such as time delays, crosstalk at connectors and cablicng schemes
- digitization including ADC, dead times and readout

On the analysis side it must be emphasized that the SPMT subsystem will be capable of providing high-level crosschecks to the JUNO results by measuring the solar oscillation parameters. In this direction the Brazilian groups are involved in a careful estimation of the expected sensitivity to such parameters using both Bayesian and Frequentist statistical methods.

5 List of the interested scientists in the community

- Chile Team
 - Engineers:
 - * Rafael Herrera, mechanical engineer (FT)
 - * Pablo Walker, electronics engineer (FT)
 - * Ignacio Jeria, mechanical engineer (PT)
 - Students: Agustín Campeny, undergraduate EE student
 - Faculty:
 - * Giancarlo Troni, expert in underwater autonomous vehicles

- * Angel Abusleme, expert in electronics for particle physics experiments
- Brazilian Team
 - Faculty
 - * Hiroshi Nunokawa (PUC-RJ), theoretician (FT)
 - * Pietro Chimenti (UEL), experimentalis (FT)
 - * Christiane Frigerio Martins (UEL), theoretician (not yet part of the collaboration, but interested to be)
 - Pos-doc: George de Conto Santos (UEL)
 - Students: Antônio Francisco Jr. (UEL, mestrado)

6 Current status and expected challenges

6.1 HVS

The HVS circuit design is complete (Fig.4). We are currently testing different coupling capacitors and different capacitor dielectrics (X7R vs C0G) in order to find out the best configuration. Some considerations are price (which is important for 25600 parts and spares), HV aging, lead time and of course, signal integrity. We are also figuring out the best mechanisms to prevent sparks in the board.

Figure 4: SPMT simplified schematic. Some component values are preliminary. Credit: Pablo Walker.

The HVS layout is completely routed. We are still working to define some passive component sizes and layer stack configuration in order to ensure the system reliability. A rendered 3-D image of the populated HVS board, top view, is presented in Fig. 5 .

The HVS layout should be finalized as soon as possible, passive components should be chosen subject to technical and economic constraints to have a Final Design Review in January 2020 presenting results from previous version in order to go to production once cleared the Production Readiness Review.

Figure 5: Rendered 3-D image of the populated HVS board, top view. 4 HVUs are on the top layer (visible), the other 4 are located on the bottom layer. The 64 MCX connectors are on the right edge. Passive components and connectors to GCU (left) and ABC board (middle top and bottom) are visible. Credit: Pablo Walker.

6.2 UWB

A first box design has been provided by the Bordeaux group (France) and then has some modifications have been foreseen to decrease possible point of failure and keeps the high integration capacity from different parts coming from different groups around the world.

The Chilean team designed, built and evaluated four different concepts as UWB prototypes, and evaluated the best option based on different metric comparison. The analysis can be visualized with the radar chart shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Radar chart of different design with the 7 topics to consider, testing simplicity, Integration, Manufacturing simplicity, Thermal dissipation, Corrosion, Mechanical Failure, Seal Design.

After selecting the prototype C1S10F, minor changes have been implemented to a final version. The final design consists of two lids (one removable), one flange

and a body made of 10 inches of SCH10 stainless steel pipe. The bottom lid and the flange are welded to the body using the TIG method, this kind of weld being cheaper than laser welding and providing lower thermal deformation than MIG. The designed flange provides a wide surface where the two axial o-rings are in contact sealing the surface. It is also required to ensure low roughness (Ra 0,8) on the surface. The top lid (removable part) is where the two axial o-rings and a single radial o-ring are mounted, increasing the sealing safety factor due to a failure of one of the o-rings. All o-ring are made of different materials:

- external axial o-ring: Viton;
- internal axial o-ring: EPDM;
- radial o-ring: Viton.

Figures 7 and 8 show the final C1s10FF model.

Figure 8: Left: C1S10FF 3-D rendering. Right: C1S10FF prototype with mounting pieces.

Review. We expect to focus on production of the 220 UWB validation and installation during 2020.

6.3 Simulation and Analysis

A first version of the electronic simulation has been implemented and refinements are in progress. The completion of the electronic simulation will require a long development period as it must be bench-marked against real data taken by the running detector.

On the analysis side, preliminary (internal) encouraging results of the analysis of SPMT sensitivity to solar parameters have been presented to the collaboration and a publication is expected in 2020.

7 Timeline

The JUNO detector construction is well under way and test runs are expected to start in June 2022. Concerning the SPMT subsystem 26000 SPMTs have already been tested and accepted well within schedule.

8 Construction and operational costs

The total expected construction cost is about 300M€, all parts already funded. The operational cost is expected to be about 7M\$ per year with a share of about 0.47% and 1.41% corresponding to respectively Brazilian and Chilean institutions. Payment of operational costs should start in 2021.

9 Computing requirements

The expected data volume per year for JUNO is 2 PB for raw data storage, 200 TB for reconstructed data, 20 TB for simulation and 1 TB for analysis. For

computing, 12000 CPU cores will be needed. All this computing power and data storage will be provided by IHEP/CAS and other European Funding agencies. It would however be useful to have a south-american cluster to process data for simulation and analysis (25TB per year of data, both simulation and analysis, and 64 cores).

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